

MetaDocencia's Accessibility Profiles

In our mission and vision, Metadocencia is defined as *“an inclusive and collaborative community”* that develops *“open, reusable and accessible resources”*. To define different accessibility profiles for reviewing the materials we offer, we work with an accessibility team: Iván Gabriel Poggio, Mariela Rajngewerc, and Patricia A. Loto.

We know that it is always possible to improve our work, which is presented as dynamic and permanent, always keeping *people* at the center of our work.

We are open to suggestions for improvements and warnings of possible barriers to accessing our material. At the end of this note you will find an email address to write to us.

We present this first description of profiles of people with disabilities to organize the different requirements and share material accessible to the greatest number of people.

Related to vision

Difficulty using sight as a means of perception.

Description	Action
Lost of vision	Facilitate voice interaction.

Low vision	Possibility of using a magnifying glass. Material with font size of at least 12 points for the text and 14 points for titles.
Color blindness	Adequate contrast of at least 4.5. Use of shapes, textures, and any other element that helps distinguish information without resorting to color.

Related to hearing

Difficulty using hearing to perceive information.

Description	Action
Lost of hearing	Captioning. If the mother tongue is sign language, interpretation in sign language; use of clear, simple, and concise written language, avoiding as far as possible unnecessary <i>adornments</i> that make understanding difficult.

Related to mobility

Variable difficulty of interaction with the device.

Description	Action
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Difficulty with control and precision regarding the interactive use of the device in which the web is executed.

Screen readers or similar specific software. Keyboard priority use.

Related to concentration and attention

Variable difficulty sustaining attention on a task for long periods of time.

Description	Action
Variable difficulty sustaining attention on a task for long periods of time	Easy-to-read content.
Task duration minimization. Frequent breaks (e.g., every 50 minutes).	

Accessibility team email: accesibilidad@metadocencia.org

References

- [Web Accessibility 1: Profiling of people with Disabilities](#)
- [Olga Carreras website on accessibility](#)